

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B049
Date: 05 Sep 2004
Take Off 09:41:53
Landing: 14:32:58
Flight Time 4h51m05

Trials Instructions: ADRIEX – radiation flight in heavy pollution over Adriatic.
Operating Area: Northern Adriatic Sea in the vicinity of the Ocean Tower at 45°18'51"N, 12°30'29"E and area within ~ 80 miles

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Ellie Highwood	Reading University
5	Flight Manager	Maureen Smith	FAAM
6	Dropsondes	Steve Devereau	FAAM
7	Core Chemistry	Doug Anderson	FAAM
8	CVI	Paul James	FAAM
9	VACC	Stuart Heath	FAAM
10	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
11	SWS	Andy Wilson	Met Office
12	Filters	Paola Formenti	CNRS/University of Paris 12
13	AMS	Paul Williams	UMIST
14	TDL / WAS / PAN / Tubes	Jim McQuaid	Leeds University
15	Nephelometer / PSAP	Jolene Cook	Reading University
16	Mission Scientist 2	Jim Haywood	Met Office
17	Mission Scientist 3	Simon Osborne	Met Office
18	CCM	Sue Angold	Directflight
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B049 Track 05-SEP-04

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B049
 Date: 05/09/04
 Project: ADRIEX
 Location: N. Adriatic

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
064500		UBBRs	-.27 kft	024	Covers Off
074336		INU	-.27 kft	024	To NAVIGATE
081357		INU	-.27 kft	024	To ALIGN
090949		INU	-.26 kft	024	To NAVIGATE
094153		T/O	1.6 kft	254	Treviso
095158	095521	Profile 1	5.0 - 2.0 kft	167	500fpm from 3kft
095708	100132	Profile 1	2.0 - 0.05 kft	344	
100325	100930	Profile 2	0.05 - 3.1 kft	173	500fpm
100940	101633	Profile 2	3.3 - 10.0 kft	167	1000fpm
101858	102438	Profile 2	10.0 - 15.0 kft	358	
103032		Sonde	15.0 kft	349	Launch 01, on RFC
103247	103755	Profile 3	15.0 - 10.0 kft	170	1000fpm
103756	103925	Run 1	10.0 - 10.2 kft	165	climb 300ft
103932	104800	Run 1	10.2 kft	166	
104951	105544	Profile 4	10.4 - 4.7 kft	343	
105544	110756	Run 2	4.7 kft	354	
110939	111212	Profile 5	4.7 - 2.5 kft	178	1000fpm to 3kft
111218	111353	Profile 5	2.4 - 2.0 kft	177	500fpm
111353	112527	Run 3	2.0 kft	180	Into Sun
112735	113054	Profile 6	2.0 kft - 100ft	007	500fpm 2kft - 100ft
113054	114055	Run 4	100ft	008	
114158		PSAP	0.12 kft	347	Change Filter
114631	114800	Orbit 1	500ft	323	40deg, RH, start 330
114929	115059	Orbit 2	500ft	140	Start 150
115211	115336	Orbit 3	500ft	297	Start 300
115441	115610	Orbit 4	500ft	077	Start 090
120323	120449	Orbit 5	500ft	148	40deg, RH, start 150
120549	120716	Orbit 6	500ft	228	Start 240
120821	120948	Orbit 7	500ft	328	Start 330
121101	121226	Orbit 8	500ft	040	Start 060
121707	122709	Run 5	100ft	161	
122730	123003	Profile 7	0.10 - 2.0 kft	158	
123148	124149	Run 6	2.0 kft	343	
124330	124506	Profile 8	2.0 - 2.7 kft	160	500fpm
124527	124656	Profile 8	3.1 - 5.0 kft	159	1000fpm
124657	130204	Run 7	5.0kft	155	
130348	130902	Profile 9	5.0 - 10.0 kft	333	
130636		Videos	7.5 kft	330	Change Tapes
130915	132107	Run 8	10.0 - 10.5 kft	331	
132135	132641	Profile 10	10.5 - 15.0 kft	338	1000fpm
133711	134519	Profile 11	15.0 - 7.7 kft	152	1000fpm
134720	135423	Profile 11	7.7 - 1.0 kft	329	
135650	135747	Orbit 9	1000ft	036	55deg, RH, start 060
135830	135930	Orbit 10	1000ft	156	Start 150
140038	140129	Orbit 11	1000ft	338	Start 330
140204	140252	Orbit 12	1000ft	021	Start 060, 58 bank
140533	141048	Profile 12	1.0 - 6.0 kft	161	1000fpm
141302	141626	Profile 12	6.0 - 9.0 kft	314	1000fpm
143258		Land	-.19 kft	027	Treviso
143650		GPS Posn	-.19 kft	027	45'39.20N, 012'12.13E

B049 Track 05-SEP-04

FAAM Sortie Brief

Flight number: B049

Date 4th September 2004

Purpose: ADRIEX flight over Northern Adriatic and along the Po Valley

Weather: Predominantly cloud free. Heavy pollution preferred.

Flight pattern

1. Take off Treviso 08:00Z
2. Transit to Point A at low level but including period at 5000ft (10mins)
3. Interrupted profile ascent from 50' to FL150 over point A. (Ocean Tower: 45°18'50''N, 12°30'28''E) (30mins)
4. Dropsonde #1 at FL150
5. Stacked profile descent with ~4 SLRs of 10 minute duration oriented into and down sun at various levels to be determined by the aircraft scientist over point A (90 mins) Info/Dn Sun
10250
FL90
50
6. Set of banked orbits over point A at the solar zenith angle (~40deg) at 500ft or above any marine boundary layer pollution as advised by the aircraft scientist. (100mins) 2000' R3
100'
7. Holding pattern for 10 minutes (110mins)
8. Set of banked orbits over point A at the solar zenith angle (~40deg) at 500ft or above any marine boundary layer pollution as advised by the aircraft scientist. (100mins)
9. Interrupted profile ascent from 500ft to 3000ft over point A (110mins)
10. SLR at 3000ft from A to point B (44°30'N, 12°00'E) (125 mins)
11. SLR at 3000ft from B to point C at Soave (45°25'N, 11°15'E) (145 mins)
12. SLR at 3000ft from C to point D at Reggio Nell Emilia (44°42'N, 10°32'E) (160 mins)
13. SLR at 3000ft from D to point E at (45°30'N, 10°00'E) (175 mins)
14. Profile ascent to FL150 from E to point D (190mins)
15. Profile descent to FL150 to 3000ft from D to point C (205mins)
16. SLR at 3000ft from C to point B (225mins)
17. SLR at 3000ft from B to point A (240mins)
18. Set of banked orbits over point A at the solar zenith angle (~40deg) at 500ft or above any marine boundary layer pollution as advised by the aircraft scientist. (260mins)
19. Holding pattern for 10 minutes (270mins)
20. Set of banked orbits over point A at the solar zenith angle (~40deg) at 500ft or above any marine boundary layer pollution as advised by the aircraft scientist. (280mins)
21. Interrupted profile ascent from 50ft to FL150 over point A (295mins)
22. Dropsonde #2 at FL150
23. Recover to Treviso.

Point A Ocean Tower	45°18'50''N, 12°30'28''E
Point B	44°30'N, 12°00'E
Point C (Soave)	45°25'N, 11°15'E
Point D (Reggio Nell Emilia)	44°42'N, 10°32'E
Point E	45°30'N, 10°00'E

Sortie Debrief

Flight Number: B049

Date: 5th September 2004

Sortie Objectives: ADRIEX radiation flight in heavy pollution over Adriatic.

Operating area: Northern Adriatic Sea in the vicinity of the Ocean Tower at 45°18'51''N, 12°30'29'E and area within ~ 80 miles.

Weather: Clear skies over operating region, although Cu over land areas, especially to North and East. Very hazy

Flight Patterns:

Take off from Treviso at ~08:00. Very hazy. Transit to point A at 5000ft. Profile descent to low level and profile ascent from 50' to FL150. A well mixed marine boundary layer was visible, with a change in aerosol characteristics around 4000ft. The aerosol top was clearly defined around 7000ft, although another very thin layer was seen and detected at high altitude on this first profile (Alaskan haze?). Dropsonde number 1 was released over the ocean tower from FL150. A stacked descent consisting of straight and level runs oriented into- and down- sun at 10300ft (in elevated pollution layer), 5000ft, 2000ft and 100ft was performed with SWS filters in and PCASP heaters on. Two sets of 4 banked orbits (at solar zenith angle ~ 40deg) were performed at 5000ft. A stacked ascent with SLRs oriented up and down the Adriatic was then performed with SWS filters out and SWS oriented to look down to characterise the sea surface reflectance. PCASP heaters off. No sign of the elevated layer was visible in this profile, in contrast to the earlier descent. A profile ascent to FL150 repositioned us over point A. Dropsonde 2 was not launched due to the prohibitive length of waiting for clearance from Venice air traffic control. A profile descent to 1000ft was followed by 4 "super-orbits" performed at a bank angle of 55-61 degrees). Finally a profile ascent was completed to 9000ft above the aerosol layer before recovery to Treviso.

Summary:

A very successful flight for radiation measurements in near perfect meteorological and pollution conditions. Good orbits and into-and down sun runs. Lower BBRs measured ~55Wm⁻² during 100ft runs, and showed correlation with aerosol on others. Aerosol optical depth from the ground measurements was ~0.43, and our observations of the aerosol layer agreed qualitatively with the lidar. Mystery elevated layer possibly large particles, but very few in number. Not detected on return. Nephelometer appears to be logging better after changing the DLU during the down day.

Problems:

15 minutes of missing data from AMS, but no vacuum was lost. PCASP (wing mounted) is missing the first three channels.

FL100 15min $\nearrow$ FL150 Sonde 02
 $\searrow$ 1000'
'A'

set of 4 orbits $\pm 5^\circ$

1008, 3 1/2,

3 1/2

Aircraft Scientist's LogFlight No **B049**.....Date **5/9/04**.....Page **1**..... of **6**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	401			TREVISO	Note: T/O delayed due to mechanical issues on plane
0944	T/O			TREVISO	Very hazy, Cirrus to RH of aircraft, distant. Clear below, low visibility haze to at least 5000ft.
095158	P1 ↓	15000ft			Very hazy,
095409		3000ft			Ci to left of plane
095524	P1 ↓	2000ft	165		haze interrupt
095718	P1 ↓				recurrence
095925					Sea state 2? Haze
100027		600ft			Passing over ship track.
100132	P1 and	50ft			clear above
100326	P2	50'			T-φ gam, stable layer,
100742		2000			mid & high level to left, haze
101825		10000			
101857	P2	10000			recurrence, to Cu over land & Ci
102045		11640			over land, very thin well defined layer above tops of Cu Neph peak @ 10250ft, large particles from A but very few. CO also shows

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B049**.....

 Date **5/9/04**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
103756					1st 1/2 out of plume,
104000		10300			2nd part 1040 peaks
					79-84 CO well
					correlated with neph
104633		10300			
104800	Rland	10300			
105002	P4↓	10300 →5000			Well defined neph & CO plume.
					WAS bottles & filters
					Cu over land
					Thin high alt layer visible
					above clouds
105545	P4↓	5000			
105545	R2	5000			hazy layer below
105849	R2	5000			CN 3000, PSASP 500
					Mid & high level cloud to
					right
110856	R2	5000			turning right, dark layer visible
48					above.
110939	P5↓	5000 →2000			Hazy - no horizon ahead
111440	P5ord				
111840	R3	2000			Core chem calib @ start of run
					SWS good data in this period.
					Hazy, clear above & below
11224		2000			OJings to RH S of rocket.
					Hazy, mid & high level to

the LHS

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
112527	R3 end				Oil rigs ahead & below (gas platforms)
112735	R6	2000 → 100ft			
113054	R4	100ft			Sea state 1,2 Core chain calib. Some SWS orientation problems
113725					Cloud to east, not interfering
114054	↗	400ft	330		500ft orbits due to boats
114651	01				40° SZA SWS filters in
114800	02	400ft			end orbit 1 clear above
114930	02	400ft	150		clear above, ocean blue visible
115039	02				End orbit 2
115216	03		300		clear above 40° SZA
115334	03				end orbit 3
115442	04		090		end orbit 4
		600ft			SWS filters out Holding pattern
120320	start 05	500ft	150		SWS out, SZA @ 40 clear above
120457	end 05				— —
120548	06	500ft	240		SZA @ 40 clear above
120717	end 06	500ft			Haze thinner than earlier in flight.
120820	07	500ft	330		
120948	07				End of orbit

9.44
1215

150 mins
210
220

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
121100	08	500ft	060		Start orbit
121223	08	500ft			End orbit
			155		SWS filters out, 6° angle to avoid pitch ↓ to sea surface
					Core chem calib @ start of run
					PCASP heaters off
121708	R5	100ft			BBRs 50 Wm ⁻² as expected
122037					Core chem calib done
122557					BBRs dropping away from coast range 59 → 54
122730	R5				Peak in nephs at end is power station??
122730	P7	100 → 200			Clouds to left hand side
123000	P7				End profile, turn to return to pt A.
123147	R6	2000	338		Start of run.
124335	P8	2000 -5000			
124703	R7	5000	155		Start of run
					Missing chunk in 1255 ^{cepst} 1255-1258
					regained @ 13.01.33
					High cloud to left.
130202	R7	5000			
130358	P9				Drop off of O ₃ & CO in last few seconds
130908	R8	12100			Run to lode for phone

165mins

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
132157					
132135	P107 FL100-FL150				Climbing out of pollution layer pretty consistent.
					# Very hazy below
132442					Cu to above level of mountains, capping haze now, separate layer no longer visible, some Ci above over land, but not affecting mn.
132639	P107 FL150				
					Dropsonde #2 aborted due to 2 much traffic
					Holding pattern @ FL150 due to aircraft traffic.
					Cloud over land, Cu at Ci over mountains
133712	P111				Profile descent
133929					Darkey/brown haze by visible below.
134520		8000ft.			Interrupt P11, turn toward A
					Brown aerosol layer with clean str above but under tops of Cu. Some evidence of layering in structure

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
134720	P11				Recommence profile back towards A.
		7000ft			well defined top to cloud layer @ 7000ft in neph → earlier high layer not visible at this time in P11.
					Evidence of layering in neph peak @ 7000ft, gap @ 6, then rising again as descent end
135424	P11	1000ft			
135650	09				
13	010				4 Orbits @ SZA +17 SWS filters out (up to 61° bank)
135830	010				
	0				
140038	011				
140204	012				
140533	P12	¹⁰⁰⁰ → 9000ft			out of top of haze layer Tall Cu to north-east over land.
141636	P12 end	9000ft			End of profile. Haze layers clearly visible

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B049

Date: 5/9/04

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
09:51:50	600		0	5							Start Profile 1 from 5000'
09:52:16	660			3							4000'
09:53:45	980		Overheat	5							3000'
09:55:26	1000			3							2000'
09:58:50	1050			3							1000'
10:00:40	900			5							500'
10:01:34	1000			10							End of Profile 1 @ 50'
10:03:26	890			10							Start Profile 2 from 50'
10:06:10	820			5							FL010
10:08:14	800			5							FL020
10:09:25	610			5							FL030
10:10:25	500			2							FL040
10:11:28	450		On	2							FL050
10:12:24	360		0	2							FL060
10:13:26	100			1							FL070
10:14:25	5										FL080
10:15:27	5										FL090
10:16:35	5										FL100
10:20:10	5										FL110
10:21:20	5										FL120
10:22:30	5										FL130
10:23:35	3										FL140
10:24:43	5										End of Profile 2 @ FL150
10:32:51	3										Start Profile 3 from FL150
10:33:55	15										FL140
10:35:05	15										FL130
10:36:01	15										FL120
10:36:51	60										FL110
10:37:58											End of P3 Start Run1 @ FL100
10:38:00	30			1							
10:40:00	10										
10:42:00	60			2							

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

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Date: 5/9/04

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
10:44:00	55			2							
10:46:00	5										
10:47:51											End Of Run1
10:49:55											Start Profile 4 from FL100
10:51:22	5										FL090
10:52:30											FL080
10:53:45	85			1							FL070
10:54:35	360			2							FL060
10:55:45											End of P4 Start Run2 @ 5000'
10:56:00	500			2							
10:58:00	460			2							
11:00:00	700			2							
11:02:00	570			2							
11:04:00	560			5							
11:06:00	515			2							
11:07:57											End of Run 2
11:09:40											Start Profile 5 from 5000'
11:10:49	660			5							4000'
11:12:00	1020			5							3000'
11:13:56	1030			5							End of P5 Start Run 3 @ 2000'
11:14:00	1040			5							
11:16:00	1000			5							
11:18:00	800			5							
11:20:00	800			5							
11:22:00	760			5							
11:24:00	800			5							
11:25:27											End of Run 3
11:27:35	850			5							Start Profile 6 from 2000'
11:29:23	850			5							1000'
11:30:55											End of P6 Start Run 4 @ 100'
11:31:00	950			5							
11:33:00	900			5							

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

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Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
11:35:00	860			5							
11:37:00	850			5							
11:39:00	830		Overheat	5							
11:40:58											End of Run 4
11:46:31											Start Orbits
11:56:10											End of Orbits
12:03:23											Start Orbits
12:12:26											End Orbits
12:17:10			On								Start Run 5 @ 100'
12:18:00	860			5							
12:20:00	930			5							
12:22:00	850			5							
12:24:00	1000			5							
12:26:00	950			5							
12:27:10											End Run 5 Start Profile 7 from 100'
12:28:30	940			5							1000'
12:30:05	740			5							End of Profile 7 @ 2000'
12:31:48			Overheat								Start Run 6 @ 2000'
12:32:00	780			5							
12:34:00	800			3							
12:36:00	1000			3							
12:38:00	950			3							
12:40:00	800			5							
12:41:49											End of Run 6
12:43:31	680			5							Start Profile 8 from 2000'
12:44:59	640			5							3000'
12:46:00	580			5							4000'
12:47:00			On								End of P8 Start Run 7 @ 5000'
12:48:00	600			5							
12:50:00	660			5							
12:52:00	680			5							
12:54:00	780			5							

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
12:56:00	100		0	1							
12:58:00	200			1							
13:00:00	800			1							
13:02:00											
13:02:08											End of Run 7
13:03:50											Start Profile 9 from 5000'
13:05:21	7			1							FL060
13:06:13	8										FL070
13:07:06	8										FL080
13:08:04											FL090
13:09:05											End of P9 Start Run 8 @ FL100
13:10:00	10										
13:12:00	4										
13:14:00	10										
13:16:00	15										
13:18:00	10										
13:20:00											
13:21:10											End of Run 8
13:21:38											Start Profile 10 from FL100
13:22:21	7										FL110
13:23:18	3										FL120
13:24:16	3										FL130
13:25:27	3										FL140
13:26:40	3										End of Profile 10 @ FL150
13:37:16	Noise										Start Profile 11 @ FL150
13:38:20	10										FL140
13:39:07	10										FL130
13:40:10	15										FL120
13:41:23	20										FL110
13:42:32	25										FL100
13:43:43	35										FL090
13:44:51	30										FL080

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B049

Date: 5/9/04

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
13:48:01	810		3								FL070
13:48:56	650		5								FL060
13:49:57	800		3								FL050
13:50:52	780		3								FL040
13:51:51	1000		5								FL030
13:53:15	950		5								2000'
13:54:26	1170		5								End of Profile 11 @ 1000'
13:56:55											Start Orbits
14:03:38											End of Orbits
14:05:38	600		5								Start Profile 12 From 1000'
14:07:00	560		5								FL020
14:07:43	450		5								FL030
14:08:36	300		2								FL040
14:09:41	420		2								FL040
14:10:53	60										FL050
14:14:25	35										FL060
14:15:21	2										FL070
14:16:29											FL080
											End of Profile 12 @ FL090

SWS/SHIMS PRE-FLIGHT LOG		Date	5/9/04	Flight	B 049
Operator(s)	A. WILSON		Campaign	ADRIEX	
Departure	05094155 Z		Arrival	05143300 Z	

Physical system setup

Module Number Serial.	Connection(e.g.SWS nir, SHIMS upper)
0	SWS NIR
27581	SWS VIS

System functionality check **After system stabilizes**

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} +$	0 secs	at time	074600Z
Freezer temp	-7°C	@	074600Z	

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight # **B 049** Date **5/9/04** Operator(s) **A. Wilson** log page **1** of **1**

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	MIRR Pos	Int Times		Remarks
				Vis	NIR	

074715 Z						DARK current - PRE TAKE-off
075215 Z						DATA START
075500 Z						VIDEO START
081100 Z						TAKE off Delayed by 1 Hour due to hydraulics problem!!
						VIDEO STOP - rewind &
085800 Z						DATA STOP
091500 Z						ND3.0 Filters fitted to vis & NIR * Prior to flight.
092706 Z			90°A			VIDEO START
092748 Z			90°A			DATA START - DARK current
093000 Z			90°A	Auto		DATA START
094155 Z			90°A			TAKE off
094205 Z			0°			
095330 Z	P1	030	180°	Auto		
095158	P1	050 → 03	0°	Auto		start P1 → 50ft.
095330	P1	030	180°	Auto		
	P1	020	180	Auto		int P1
095708	P1	020	180°	Auto		restart P1
100132	P1	50ft	180°	Auto		end P1
100325	P2	50ft	180°	Auto		Start P2 → FL150
101640	P2	FL100	180°	Auto		int P2
101900	P2	100	180°	Auto		restart P2
102445	P2	150	180°	Auto		end P2
103032		150	180°	Auto		Sonde 1 launched
103247	P3	150	180°	Auto		
103610	P3	11500	43°F	Auto		
103756	P3	100	46°F	Auto		End P3
	R1	100	46°F	Auto		into sun run.
104900	R1	10300ft	46°F	Auto		end run 1
105002	P4	103	32°A	Auto		P4 FL103 → 5000ft
105550	P4	5000ft	31°A	Auto		
	R2	5000ft	31°A	Auto		Down sun run. Zenith 38° Pitch 68°
110756	R2	5000ft	31°A	Auto		Signal strengths appeared down. Video shows possible condensation?
110939	P5	5000ft	42°F	Auto		start P5 → 2000ft.
111353	P5	2000ft	45°F	Auto		end P5
1118353	R3	2000ft	45°F	Auto		Start R3 into sun run
112527	R3	2000ft	45°F	Auto		end R3
112735	P6	2000ft	33°A	Auto		start P6 → 100ft down sun profile.
113054	P6	100ft	33°A	Auto		
	R4		33°A	Auto		start R4

*
Filters fitted

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight # **B 049** Date **5/9/04** Operator(s) **A. Wilson** log page **2** of **3**

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	MIRR Pos	Int Times		Remarks
				Vis	NIR	

114055	R4	100ft	33°	Auto		end R4
114631	orbit 1	500ft	6°F	10	30	Start orbit 1, 40° right wing down
114800	" 1	500ft	6°F	10	30	end 1
114929	" 2	500ft	6°F	10	30	Start 2
115059	" 2	500ft	6°F	10	30	end 2
115211	" 3	500ft	6°F	10	30	start 3
115336	" 3	500ft	6°F	10	30	end orbit 3
115441	" 4	500ft	6°F	10	30	start 4
115610	" 4					end 4
120210						* Filters removed.
120323	orbit 5	500ft	6°F	10	10	start orbit 5 40° right wing down
120449	" "	400ft	6°F	10	10	end 5
120549	" 6	400ft	6°F	10	10	start 6
120716	" 6	400ft	6°F	10	10	end orbit 6
120821	" 7	400ft	6°F	10	10	Start orbit 7
120948	" 7	400ft	6°F	10	10	end 7
121101	" 8	400ft	6°F	10	10	start 8
121226	" 8	400ft				
121350			180°	Auto		looking downward to characterise Sea surface
121500	R5		174°A	Auto		correct per Aircraft Pitch.
121707	R5	100ft	174°A	Auto		end start R5 @ 100ft
122709	R5	100ft	174°A	Auto		end R5
122730	P7	100ft	174°A	Auto		start P7 → 200ft
123000						Video stop
123005	P7	200ft	174°A	Auto		end P7
123054						Video start
123148	R6	200ft	174°A	Auto		Start of R6 @ 200ft
124149	R6	200ft	174°A	Auto		end R6
124330	P8	200ft	174°A	Auto		start P8 → 500ft
124657	P8	500ft	174°A	Auto		end P8 @ 500ft
	R7	500ft	174°A			start R7 @ 500ft.
	R7					end R7
130348	P9	500ft	174°A	Auto		Start P9 → PL100
130902	P9	10000	174°A	Auto		end P9 @ PL100
	R8	100	174°A	Auto		start R8
132107	R8	100	174°A	Auto		
132135	P10	100	174°A	Auto		start P10 → PL150
132641	P10	150	174°A	Auto		end P10 @ PL150
	P11	150	176°A	Auto		
	P11	080	176°A	Auto		int P11
	P11	080	176°A	Auto		
	P11	100ft	176°A	Auto		

Filters fitted

Filters NOT fitted

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 049	Date	5/9/04	Operator(s)	A. Wilson	log page	3	of	3
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks			
				Vis	NIR				

†
 Filters
 Not
 Fitted

135650	orbit 9								Start 55°
135747	" 9	1000ft	6°F	10	10				end
135830	" 10	1000ft	6°F	10	10				Start 10
135930	" 10	1000ft	6°F	10	10				end 10
140038	" 11	1000ft	6°F	10	10				Start 11 bank 58°
140129	" 11	1000ft	6°F	10	10				end 11
140204	" 12	1000ft	6°F	10	10				Start 12 bank 60.5° Right
140252	" 12	1000ft	6°F	10	10				end orbit 12
140533	P12	1000ft	174°A	10	10				P12 → P1090
141048	P12	060	174°A	Auto					int-P12
141302	P12	060	174°A	Auto					Restart P12
141942									DARK CURRENT
									DATA STOP
142340									VIDEO STOP
143300Z									LANDING

Winds down

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG

FLIGHT: B049	DATE: 5/09/2004	OPERATOR: Doug Anderson	PAGE: 1 of 2
LOCATION: Northern Adriatic Sea in the vicinity of the Ocean Tower at 45o18'51"N, 12o30'29'E and area within ~ 80 miles		PROJECT: ADRIEX – radiation flight in heavy pollution over Adriatic.	

GAS CYLINDER PRESSURES	Argon/CO2	N2	CO	HORACE
PRE FLIGHT	2140 psi / 149 barR	1310 psi / 91 bar	630 psi / 45 bar	-- n/a --
POST FLIGHT	psi / bar	psi / bar	psi / bar	-- n/a --

TIME (GMT)	HEIGHT (Flight Level)	RUN #	CO SENSITIVITY (Hz/ppbV)	CO BACKGROUND (ppb)	CO BCKGRD.CNT.B (Hz)	CO CONC. (ppb V)	O3 (ppb)	NO (ppb)	NO2 (ppb)	NOx (ppb)	SO2 (ppb)			
03/09/04	FL150	-	89.99	56.06	5045.13	61.376	-	-	-	-	-			
15:00:50	Remarks: Last calibration from previous flight/ground test for comparison with today.													
05/09/04	ground	-	90.03	57.78	5201.69	-	-	-	-	-	-			
05:44:46	Remarks: First cal of day Air sample pipe (ASP) closed. CO cal max values : 567 – 527													
06:02:26	Ground	-	86.75	59.75	5183.35	-	-	-	-	-	-			
	Remarks: ASP closed. CO cal max values : 515 – 503													
06:23:38	ground	-	83.81	61.34	5141.35	-	-	-	-	-	-			
	Flow Lamp:	33.90	Press Monocr	0.63	Press Cell:	7.14	Press Cal Gas	2.46	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	26.22	PMT °C	26.16
	Remarks: ASP closed. CO cal max values : 512 – 505													
06:31:28	ground	-	82.68	62.20	5142.54	212.449	-	-	-	-	-			
	Remarks: ASP closed. CO cal max values : 517 – 522													
07:32:16	ground	-	84.06	61.66	5183.32	-	-	-	-	-	-			
	Remarks: ASP closed. CO cal max values : 534 - 539													
07:40:44	ground	-	84.44	61.35	5179.95	-	-	-	-	-	-			
	Remarks: ASP closed. CO cal max values :													
08:00:59	ground	-	90.57	60.16	5448.81	189.362	-	-	-	-	-			
	Flow Lamp:	33.96	Press Monocr	0.63	Press Cell:	7.14	Press Cal Gas	2.25	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	26.14	PMT °C	26.11
	Remarks: Post Power changeover reboot and cal. ASP closed. CO cal max values : 593 - 562													
08:05:43	ground	-	85.59	61.75	5284.57	-	-	-	-	-	-			
	Remarks: ASP closed. CO cal max values : 470 – 500 2 nd cal to ensure CO max is within range (can't see HORACE display from belted in position). It is now a little low!													
09:03:38	ground	-	84.28	61.85	5212.70	-	-	-	-	-	-			
	Remarks: ASP closed. CO cal max values : 513 – 521 Delay due to hydraulic problems													
09:33:25	ground	Taxiing	87.60	61.17	5358.43	164.229	50	0.11	2.43	2.54	4.99			
	Flow Lamp:	33.94	Press Monocr	0.62	Press Cell:	7.13	Press Cal Gas	2.25	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	26.15	PMT °C	26.10
	Remarks: CO cal max values : 545 – 562 Post power change cal													
09:38:25	ground	Pre t/o	85.10	62.04	5279.96	162.206	50	0.05	2.22	2.27	5.24			
	Remarks: ASP closed. CO cal max values : 508 - 513													
09:51:34	FL050	-	83.82	62.14	5208.74	118.864	61	0.00	0.70	0.70	4.54			
	Flow Lamp:	33.87	Press Monocr	0.61	Press Cell:	7.14	Press Cal Gas	2.24	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	26.36	PMT °C	26.31
	Remarks: ASP open. CO cal max values : 515 - 519													
10:05:17	100'	In turn & into P2	83.59	62.33	5210.43	146.518	75	0.04	0.80	0.84	4.31			
	Flow Lamp:	33.88	Press Monocr	0.63	Press Cell:	7.16	Press Cal Gas	2.26	Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C	
	Remarks: CO cal max values : 522 – 527 Cal ended @ FL010.													
10:28:37	FL150	-	83.81	60.98	5110.94	70.715	62	0.06	0.21	0.27	5.18			
	Remarks: CO cal max values : 522 – 527													
10:52:15	FL013	Into P4	85.41	60.32	5151.96	67.422	49	-0.03	0.17	0.13	4.33			
	Remarks: CO cal max values : 531 – 537 P4 started 10:50:02, roughly half way through calibration. Cal ended @ FL085													
11:17:40	FL020	Into R3	87.24	59.62	5201.26	148.380	79	-0.05	1.04	0.99	4.38			
	Flow Lamp:	33.91	Press Monocr	0.63	Press Cell:	7.15	Press Cal Gas	2.26	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	25.76	PMT °C	25.71
	Remarks: CO cal max values : 535 - 541													
11:35:12	FL001		87.81	58.94	5175.50	159.214	76	-0.01	0.97	0.96	4.08			
	Remarks: CO cal max values : 527 - 532													
12:01:06	FL004		86.71	59.55	5163.54	156.761	74	-0.04	1.14	1.09	5.06			
	Flow Lamp:	33.95	Press Monocr	0.62	Press Cell:	7.14	Press Cal Gas	2.26	Lamp °C	-	Monocr °C	-	PMT °C	-
	Remarks: CO cal max values : 532 - 527													
12:20:52	FL001	R5	86.19	59.36	5116.41	155.349	74	-0.01	1.11	1.09	4.98			
	Remarks: CO cal max values : 524 - 520													

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG

FLIGHT: B049	DATE: 5/09/2004	OPERATOR: Doug Anderson	PAGE: 2 of 2
LOCATION: Northern Adriatic Sea in the vicinity of the Ocean Tower at 45o18'51"N, 12o30'29'E and area within ~ 80 miles		PROJECT: ADRIEX – radiation flight in heavy pollution over Adriatic.	

TIME (GMT)	HEIGHT (Flight Level)	RUN #	CO SENSITIVITY (Hz/ppbV)	CO BACKGROUND (ppb)	CO BCKGRD.CNT.B (Hz)	CO CONC. (ppb V)	O3 (ppb)	NO (ppb)	NO2 (ppb)	NOx (ppb)	SO2 (ppb)		
12:35:23	FL020	Into R6	85.61	59.17	5065.16	96.710	79	0.04	1.08	1.12	4.91		
	Flow Lamp:	33.99	Press Monocr	0.62	Press Cell:	7.15	Press Cal Gas	2.25	Lamp °C	-	Monocr °C	-	PMT °C
Remarks: CO cal max values : 520 - 523													
12:50:49	FL050	R7	84.41	59.71	5040.11	129.943	69	-0.05	0.94	0.90	4.13		
	Remarks: CO cal max values : 526 - 523												
13:12:58	FL103	R8	84.14	59.59	5014.29	-	-	-	-	-	-		
	Remarks: CO cal max values :												
13:30:31	FL150	-	84.98	58.70	4988.94	110.211	64	-0.16	0.39	0.23	5.25		
	Remarks: CO cal max values : 529 - 532												
14:21:13	FL090	-	88.00	57.23	5036.04	69.671	54	0.04	0.20	0.18	4.03		
	Remarks: CO cal max values : Descent to FL050												

Flight Manager's In-Flight Log

Flight No B..049...

Date ...5.9.04.....

Page ...1... of ...1...

Video Tapes	GPS	INU	DRS
V8	Lat 45'39.20N	45'39.18N	☐
No.	Long 012'12.11E	12'12.13E	HORACE ☒
Ends	Time 06:38:02	06:37:31	SATCOM ☒
FFC / RFC / DFC / UFC	Status ✓	ALIGN	

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
094153	TAKE OFF	from	TREVISO					
095352	P1	3000'	reduce r.o.d to 500 fpm					
	P1	Intercept @ 2000'						095158 2000' 1027mb
101640	FL100	Int	P2	→				
101900	FL100	Recom	P2	→	1000 fpm			0 400ft
104800								
105002	FL103	start	P4					R3, P5
105550		END:	P4	1ST RUN 2.	FL 5000			R4, P6
113920		Hermann cal,	before and	R4				
								1021.355 a 1020.128 b
1		PSAP Pump OFF						
	O2	start	150°					
	O5	start	150°					33ms
122730	P7	starts.						
								5+10 = 15ms → 150 seconds
	O9	060° start	hdg.					↓
143258	Land	at	Trevise		<u>4h 55</u>			
								→ Alison order Vid Tapes